

Syntheses and characterization of the coordination compounds of metal ions of first and second transition series with the Schiff base in aqueous and non-aqueous reaction conditions

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Abstract : The coordination compounds of some metal ions of first and second transition series with the Schiff base, LH₃ (1) (obtained from the nucleophilic addition reaction between acetoacetanilide and *o*-hydroxybenzylamine followed by the elimination of one H₂O molecule) in aqueous and non-aqueous reaction conditions have been synthesized. An aqueous or MeOH solution of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} ions reacts with an alkaline solution of 1 in 1 : 2 molar ratio and forms the monomeric coordination compounds, [Cu(LH₂)₂] (2), [Zn(LH₂)₂] (3), [Mn(LH₂)₂(H₂O)₂] (4), [Zr(OH)₂(LH₂)₂] (5) and [MoO₂(LH₂)₂] (6) respectively. On the other hand, a MeOH solution of the above metal ions and 1 in 1 : 1 molar ratio in the presence of MeONa form the coordination compounds, [Cu(LH)]₂ (7), [Zn(LH)(MeOH)] (8), [Mn(LH)(MeOH)₃] (9), [Zr(OH)₂(LH)(MeOH)] (10) and [MoO₂(LH)(MeOH)] (11) respectively. The coordination compounds have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molecular weight, molar conductance, spectral (IR, reflectance, ¹H NMR and ESR) studies and the magnetic susceptibility measurements. 1 behaves as a monobasic bidentate ON donor ligand in 2-6 coordinating through its phenolic O and azomethine N atoms, while as a dibasic tridentate ONO donor ligand in 7-11 coordinating through its phenolic O, azomethine N and enolic O atoms. The coordination compounds of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} ions are paramagnetic, while those of remaining ions are diamagnetic. A square-planar structure to 2, 7; a tetrahedral structure to 3, 8 and an octahedral structure to 4-6 and 9-11 are proposed.

Keywords : Acetoacetanilide, coordination compounds, *o*-hydroxybenzylamine, magnetic studies, Schiff base, spectral studies.

Introduction

The compounds possessing 1,3-diketone moiety have been used as model compounds in bioinorganic studies¹. They have been shown to have a wide assortment of pharmacological activities, like antibacterial², antiviral³, insecticidal⁴, anti-oxidant⁵ and prophylactic antitumor⁶. A number of β-diketones have been used as breast cancer chemo-preventive blocking agents⁷, antiestrogenic agents⁸ and anticarcinogenic agents⁹. The properties of β-diketones to form the coordination compounds with the metal ions have played an important role in various biological func-

tions of the compound, especially with antitumor activity¹⁰. The Schiff bases of 1,3-diketones in which the diketo group is linked to an alkenyl group constitute the major physiologically active principle (known generally as curcuminoids) of the traditional Indian medical plant turmeric (*Curcuma longa*, a member of Linn, Zingiberaceae family) and several other related spices¹¹. The curcuminoids, their synthetic analogues and their coordination compounds are known to exhibit anticancer, anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory activities¹². *o*-Hydroxybenzylamine is a potent γ-keto-aldehyde scavenger that has been shown

1 (keto-form)

1 (enol-form)

(2)

(3)

(4)

(5)

(6)

(7)

(8)

(9)

(10)

(11)

to protect cardiac sodium channel (Na V 1.5) from oxidant-induced inactivation. The derivatives of *o*-hydroxybenzylamine are of interest because of the structural similarities between the former and pyridoxalimine, which in its role enzymatic *trans*-amination reactions is considered to form Schiff base¹³. A perusal of the literature reveals that a number of coordination compounds of Schiff bases possessing the acetoacetanilide moiety alone¹⁴ or *o*-hydroxybenzylamine moiety alone¹⁵ are well known, however, there is no report of the coordination compounds of Schiff base derived from acetoacetanilide and *o*-hydroxybenzylamine. Keeping in view the above mentioned importance of both acetoacetanilide and *o*-hydroxybenzylamine, we thought it worth to synthesize and characterize the Schiff base, LH₃ (**1**) derived from acetoacetanilide and *o*-hydroxybenzylamine and its coordination compounds with Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} ions. We hope that the newly synthesized compounds will find extensive use in the above fields.

Results and discussion

The yellow coloured Schiff base, LH₃ (**1**) has been synthesized in EtOH by the nucleophilic addition reaction between acetoacetanilide and *o*-hydroxybenzylamine followed by the elimination of one H₂O molecule. The formation of **1** is represented as per Scheme 1 :

Scheme 1

It is soluble in MeOH, EtOH, CH₂Cl₂, CHCl₃, CCl₄, DMSO and DMF and is insoluble in H₂O. Between pH = 3–4, an aqueous or MeOH solution of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{IV} and MoO₂^{VI} ions reacts with an alkaline solution of **1** in 1 : 2 molar ratio and forms the monomeric coordination compounds, **2-6** respectively. The formations of **2-6** are represented as per Scheme 2 :

Scheme 2

A MeOH solution of the above metal ions and **1** in 1 : 1 molar ratio in the presence of MeONa form the corresponding coordination compounds, **7-11** respectively. The formations of **7-11** are represented as per Scheme 3 :

Scheme 3

The above coordination compounds are air-stable and sparingly soluble in H₂O, MeOH and EtOH but fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO. Their molar conductance values (1.7–12.8 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in 10⁻³ M DMF solution) show that they are non-electrolytes (Table 1). The

molecular weight measurements¹⁶ in diphenyl indicate the monomeric nature of **2-6**, **8-11** and the dimeric nature of **7**.

Infra-red spectral studies :

The infrared spectra of the Schiff base (**1**) and its coordination compounds (**2-11**) were recorded in KBr and the prominent peaks are shown in Table 2. The Schiff base exhibits the $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ (intramolecular H-bond), $\nu(\text{N}-$

$\text{H})$ (intramolecular H-bond), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine), $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\Phi$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (enolic) stretches at 3561, 3066, 1628, 1514 and 1200 cm^{-1} respectively. Due to the delocalization of π electrons towards the benzene ring, the $(\text{C}-\text{O})\Phi$ stretch of **1** is expected to occur at higher energy as compared to the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (enolic) stretch¹⁷. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\Phi$ stretch of **1** occurring at 1514 cm^{-1} shifts to higher energy by 5–26 cm^{-1} in **2-11** and this supports the

Table 1. Analytical, molar conductance, molecular weight and other characterization data of coordination compounds

Sl. no.	Compd.	Mol. formula	Conductance	Mol. wt. Obsd. (Calcd.)	Obsd. (Calcd.) %			
					M	C	H	N
1.	1	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	–	282 ^a (282)	–	72.48 (72.34)	6.23 (6.38)	9.83 (9.93)
2.	2	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Cu}$	3.2	633 ^b (625.5)	10.22 (10.15)	65.43 (65.23)	5.59 (5.44)	8.82 (8.95)
3.	3	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Zn}$	1.7	643 ^b (627.3)	10.33 (10.42)	65.22 (65.04)	5.68 (5.42)	8.69 (8.93)
4.	4	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{Mn}$	4.3	640 ^b (652.9)	8.58 (8.41)	62.34 (62.49)	5.79 (5.82)	8.76 (8.58)
5.	5	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{Zr}$	6.8	673 ^b (687.2)	13.32 (13.27)	59.58 (59.37)	5.22 (5.24)	8.29 (8.15)
6.	6	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{Mo}$	8.5	680 ^b (689.9)	13.77 (13.90)	59.33 (59.14)	4.90 (4.93)	8.28 (8.12)
7.	7	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{Cu}_2$	5.6	678 ^b (687)	18.32 (18.48)	59.64 (59.39)	4.52 (4.66)	8.07 (8.15)
8.	8	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Zn}$	10.2	351 ^b (377.4)	17.47 (17.30)	57.48 (57.23)	5.12 (5.30)	7.25 (7.42)
9.	9	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{Mn}$	12.8	443 ^b (430.9)	12.68 (12.74)	55.82 (55.70)	6.48 (6.50)	6.42 (6.50)
10.	10	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{Zr}$	9.1	451 ^b (437.2)	20.71 (20.86)	49.62 (49.40)	5.16 (5.03)	6.25 (6.40)
11.	11	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{Mo}$	6.7	427 ^b (439.9)	21.53 (21.81)	49.27 (49.10)	4.68 (4.55)	6.48 (6.36)

Abbreviations : ^aMass spectral data and ^bRast method data.

Table 2. Prominent IR absorption bands (cm^{-1}) of LH_3 (**1**) and its coordination compounds (**2-11**)

Sl. no.	Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine)	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic)	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (enolic)	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ MeOH	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
1.	1	1628	1514	1200	–	–	–
2.	2	1598	1521	1200	–	524	477
3.	3	1598	1519	1200	–	519	483
4.	4	1598	1521	1200	–	530	476
5.	5	1598	1519	1200	–	518	472
6.	6	1605	1520	1200	–	523	460
7.	7	1590	1540	1232	–	550	475
8.	8	1598	1524	1238	980	520	517
9.	9	1600	1524	1238	981	509	487
10.	10	1590	1522	1230	972	508	496
11.	11	1610	1523	1240	970	510	478

involvement of phenolic O atom towards coordination¹⁷. It is worth to mention that the $\nu(\text{C—O})\Phi$ stretch of **1** shifts to higher frequency by 26 cm^{-1} in **7**. The magnitude of the shift of the $\nu(\text{C—O})\Phi$ stretch of **1** by $\leq 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **2-6** and **8-11** indicates their monomeric nature, however, a positive shift of above stretch by 26 cm^{-1} ($> 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in **7** supports its dimeric structure indicating the presence of the oxo-bridge in the latter case¹⁸. The $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine) stretch of **1** occurring at 1628 cm^{-1} undergoes a negative shift by $18\text{--}38\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **2-11**, indicating the involvement of azomethine N atom towards coordination¹⁹. This downward shift is expected due to the reduction in electron density in the azomethine link on complex formation²⁰. **1** occurs in the enol form and not in the keto form as is evident by the absence of a band in the vicinity of $1650\text{--}1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [due to the $\nu(\text{C=O})$ (carbonyl) stretch] and the appearance of a band at 1200 cm^{-1} [due to the $\nu(\text{C—O})$ (enolic) stretch] in it. The appearance of $\nu(\text{C—O})$ (enolic) stretch at the same energy in **1** and **2-6** suggests the non-involvement of enolic O atom towards coordination²¹, while a positive shift by $30\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **7-11** suggests the involvement of enolic O atom towards coordination²². The appearance of non-Schiff base band in the vicinity of $508\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the $\nu(\text{M—O})$ stretch in **2-11** also supports the involvement of phenolic and/or enolic O atom towards coordination²³. The appearance of a new non-ligand band between $460\text{--}517\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the $\nu(\text{M—N})$ stretch in **2-11** also supports the involvement of azomethine N atom in coordination²¹. The increasing order of the $\nu(\text{M—N}) < \nu(\text{M—O})$ is as expected according to the greater dipole moment change in the M—O vibration, greater electronegativity of the O atom than N atom and shorter M—O bond length than the M—N bond length²⁰. The absence of a band between $850\text{--}950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of Zr=O moiety²¹ and the presence of a broad band due to the $\nu(\text{Zr—OH})$ stretch at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the present $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2^{\text{IV}}$ coordination compounds suggest their formulations as $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH}_2)_2]$ (**5**) and $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})]$ (**10**) and not as $[\text{ZrO}(\text{LH}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ and $[\text{ZrO}(\text{LH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{MeOH})]$ respectively. The appearance of a band at 1115 and 1127 cm^{-1} in **5** and **10** respectively due to the $\delta(\text{Zr—OH})$ bending mode also supports the above formulations²¹. Syamal *et al.*²⁴ have developed a non-aqueous titrimetric method to distinguish the compounds possessing the

$[\text{ZrO}]^{2+}$ or $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$ moiety. Oxozirconium(IV) compounds react with $3N$ HCl and as a result, the oxo group gets protonated, while the zirconium(IV) compounds containing $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$ moiety do not add up HCl at all. The present coordination compounds (**5** and **10**) do not react with $3N$ HCl in MeOH and this indicates the absence of Zr=O bond in these coordination compounds. The $\nu_s(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch in **6** and **11**, occur at 910 and 935 cm^{-1} respectively. On the other hand, the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch occur at 890 and 905 cm^{-1} respectively. These bands occur in the usual ranges reported for the majority of *cis*- MoO_2^{VI} coordination compounds [$\nu_s(\text{O=Mo=O})$, $892\text{--}964\text{ cm}^{-1}$] and [$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$, $840\text{--}925\text{ cm}^{-1}$]²¹. The IR data are indicative of the presence of a *cis*- MoO_2 moiety in the present cases, as a *trans*- MoO_2 structure is expected to show only the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ band since $\nu_s(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch is IR inactive²⁵. The absence of a band at $\sim 770\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the present MoO_2^{VI} coordination compounds indicates the absence of an oligomeric structure with $\cdots\text{Mo=O}\cdots\text{Mo=O}\cdots$ interaction²⁵. MeOH exhibits²⁶ the $\nu(\text{C—O})$ (alcoholic) stretch at 1034 cm^{-1} . This band shifts to the lower energy by $53\text{--}64\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting the presence of the coordinated MeOH molecule(s)²¹ in **8-11**. Thus, on the basis of the analytical data (Table 1), valence requirements and IR spectral studies, it is proposed that **1** behaves as a monobasic bidentate ON donor ligand in **2-6** coordinating through its phenolic O and azomethine N atoms, while as a dibasic tridentate ONO donor ligand in **7-11** coordinating through its phenolic O, azomethine N and enolic O atoms.

Reflectance spectral studies :

The monometallic coordination compound, **2** exhibits a broad *d-d* band centered at 18350 cm^{-1} due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition in the square-planar geometry²⁷. The dimetallic coordination compound, **7** exhibits a broad asymmetric band at 12400 cm^{-1} due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transition. The above value is much less than that observed in the majority of normal square-planar Cu^{II} coordination compounds and suggests the presence of a distorted square-planar structure²⁸. The six-coordinate high-spin Mn^{II} ion belongs to the $3d^5$ system. The Russell-Saunders term for high-spin Mn^{II} state is 6S which changes its notation to ${}^6A_{1g}$ in an octahedral environment. The coordination compounds, **4** and **9** exhibit three absorption bands at 15500 ,

19250, 24500 and 15100, 18900, 25100 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively, suggesting their octahedral geometries²⁹.

ESR spectral studies :

The ESR spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{LH}_2)_2]$ (**2**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2]$ (**7**) in DMSO at 77 K have been recorded in X-band, at frequency of 9.1 GHz under the magnetic field strength of 3000G using field modulation of 100 kHz and the g values using 100 kHz field modulation and the g values (Table 3) are relative to the standard marker, diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) ($g = 2.0036$). In frozen solution at 77 K, **2** ($S = 1/2$, $I = 3/2$) shows well resolved four hyperfine lines ($2nI + 1 = 2 \times 1 \times (3/2) + 1 = 4$) with no super-hyperfine lines. The no appearance of half field signal ($\Delta M_s = \pm 2$) corresponding to the Cu—Cu interaction rules out the presence of magnetic exchange in the

nents due to the intramolecular exchange interaction in the dimer with no super-hyperfine lines. The compound exhibits the half-field line at ~ 1600 gauss due to $\Delta M_s = 2$ transition and conclusively proves the presence of the magnetic exchange interaction in it³³. The observed values of g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp} , α^2_{Cu} and G for **7** are 2.26, 2.08, 2.13, $9.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 0.60 and 3.31 respectively. The observed value of A_{\parallel} (9.8×10^{-3}) for **7** is close to half of the value for **2** (monomer) and agrees well with the values reported for the Cu^{II} dimers involved in the magnetic exchange interaction^{28,33}. The molecular orbital coefficient, i.e. the copper-ligand covalence parameter, α^2_{Cu} (a measure of copper-ligand covalence of the in-plane σ -bonding) has been calculated using the equation³⁴.

$$\alpha^2_{\text{Cu}} = - (A_{\parallel}/0.036) + (g_{\parallel} - 2.0023) + 3/7(g_{\perp} - 2.0023) + 0.04$$

Table 3. Magnetic moments, reflectance and ESR spectral parameters of the coordination compounds

Sl. no.	Compd. (B.M.)	μ_{eff}	Reflectance spectral bands (cm^{-1})	ESR spectral parameters						
				$A_{\parallel} \times 10^{-4}$ (cm^{-1})	$A_{\perp} \times 10^{-4}$ (cm^{-1})	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	G	g_{av}	α^2_{Cu}
1.	2	1.79	18350	168	32	2.18	2.05	3.34	2.09	0.71
2.	4	5.90	15500, 19250, 24500							
3.	7	1.20	12400	98	45	2.26	2.08	3.31	2.13	0.60
4.	9	5.87	15100, 18900, 25100							

present compound and indicates its magnetically dilute nature. The observed values of g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp} , α^2_{Cu} and G for **2** are 2.18, 2.05, 2.09, $1.68 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $3.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 0.71 and 3.34 respectively. The compound possesses a square-planar structure as evident by the observed order of the values of $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0012$ and thus the ground state of Cu^{II} is predominantly $d_{x^2-y^2}$ (2B_1 as the ground state)³⁰. Here g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} denote the effective g -values when the externally applied DC field is parallel (B_{\parallel}) and perpendicular (B_{\perp}) to the symmetry axis of the crystalline field around the paramagnetic center respectively. The value of the geometric parameter (G), a measure of the exchange interaction is 3.34 and this value lies within the range³¹ (2.1–3.8), consistent with the ground state $d_{x^2-y^2}$. The value of $g_{\parallel} < 2.3$ indicates a significant covalent character in the Cu—L bond³². The spectrum of **7** in frozen solution at 77 K shows seven hyperfine lines ($2nI + 1 = 2 \times 2 \times (3/2) + 1 = 7$) in parallel compo-

A value of $\alpha^2_{\text{Cu}} = 0.5$ indicates the complete covalent bonding, while the value of $\alpha^2_{\text{Cu}} = 1.0$ suggests complete ionic bonding. The observed values ($\alpha^2_{\text{Cu}} = 0.71$ and 0.60) of the present compounds indicate that these compounds possess a significant covalent character in the Cu—L bonding³⁵.

NMR spectral studies :

The NMR spectra of the ligand (**1**), $[\text{Zn}(\text{LH}_2)_2]$ (**3**) and $[\text{Zn}(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})]$ (**8**) were recorded in DMSO- d_6 . The chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm downfield from TMS. The prominent resonance signals of **3** and **8** were compared with those of **1**. The latter exhibits signals at δ 13.42, 12.60, 9.80, 8.10, 7.23–7.45, 3.9 and 2.60 ppm due to the phenolic, enolic, $-\text{NH}$, olefinic, aromatic, $-\text{CH}_2$ and $-\text{CMe}$ protons respectively. The absence of the resonance signal due to the phenolic proton in **3** and **8** indicates the deprotonation of the phenolic OH

group followed by its involvement in coordination. The occurrence of the resonance signal at the same frequency due to the enolic proton in **1** and **3** indicates the non-involvement of the enolic group towards coordination. The absence of this signal in **8** indicates the deprotonation of the enolic OH group, followed by the involvement of its O atom in coordination. MeOH exhibits a sharp singlet at δ 4.84 ppm due to the alcoholic proton and a singlet at δ 3.35 ppm due to the methyl protons. The appearance of resonance signals at δ 2.79 ppm due to the alcoholic proton and at δ 3.2 ppm due to the methyl protons in **8** support the presence of coordinated MeOH in it. **3** does not exhibit the signals due to MeOH.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements :

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of [Cu(LH₂)₂] (**2**), [Mn(LH₂)₂(H₂O)₂] (**4**), [Cu(LH)]₂ (**7**) and [Mn(LH)(MeOH)₃] (**9**) were carried out by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the calibrant. The magnetic susceptibilities were corrected for the diamagnetism of the metal–ligand system and temperature independent paramagnetism terms (TIP)³⁶. The room temperature magnetic moments of the coordination compounds are listed in Table 3. The Cu^{II} ion belongs to the $S = \frac{1}{2}$ system and due to the presence of orbital contribution, its spin-orbit coupling constant is negative³⁷, therefore, a given magnetically dilute Cu^{II} compound is expected to exhibit magnetic moment higher than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.)³⁸. Accordingly, the experimental value of the magnetic moment (1.79 B.M.) of **2** is higher than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) which is characteristic of magnetically dilute Cu^{II} coordination compounds that have one unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital³⁹. The value of the magnetic moment and the absence of the half-field line at ~ 1600 gauss in the spectrum of the present compound indicate the magnetically dilute nature of the latter. The magnetic moment of **7** is 1.20 B.M. which is less than the expected value for one unpaired electron in each Cu^{II} ion. This lower value is indicative of the presence of anti-ferromagnetic exchange interaction between two Cu^{II} ions⁴⁰ connected by phenoxo bridges. The presence of the half-field line at ~ 1600 gauss in the ESR spectrum of **7** proves conclusively its magnetically condensed dimeric nature⁴¹. The magnetic moments of **4** and **9** are 5.90 and 5.87 B.M. respectively. These values are close to spin-only value (5.92 B.M.), indicating the presence of high-

spin, octahedral environment around the metal ions³⁹. The coordination compounds of Zn^{II} (**3**, **8**), Zr(OH)₂^{IV} (**5**, **10**) and MoO₂^{VI} (**6**, **11**) ions are diamagnetic as expected.

Experimental

Materials :

Ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate, hexadecaqua-octahydroxotetra-zirconium(IV) chloride, sodium methoxide [BDH]; manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate [Sarabhai]; zinc(II) acetate dihydrate [S. D's fine chemicals]; copper(II) acetate monohydrate [IDPL]; methanol, ethanol [Ranbaxy] and acetoacetanilide [CDH] were used as received for the syntheses. *o*-Hydroxybenzylamine, bis(acetylacetonato)-dioxomolybdenum(VI) and hexadecaqua-octahydroxotetra-zirconium(IV) acetate were prepared by adopting the published procedures⁴².

Analyses and physical measurements :

The organic skeleton of the given coordination compound (~ 0.1 g) was slowly warmed with conc. HNO₃ and then strongly decomposed [except that of MoO₂^{VI} compounds] to get a solid residue. In case of the estimation of Mn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} contents, the solid residue obtained was treated with conc. HCl to remove the excess of conc. HNO₃ and converting the residue to the respective metal chloride. The Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} contents of the respective coordination compounds were estimated by complexometric titration method against standardized EDTA solution using eriochrome black-T as the indicator. The Cu^{II} contents was estimated iodometrically against a standard solution of sodium thiosulphate to the starch end point. The Zr^{IV} contents was estimated by decomposing the organic skeleton of the respective compound with conc. HNO₃ and then igniting strongly and weighing as ZrO₂. The molybdenum contents of respective compound was estimated by decomposing the known amount (~ 0.1 g) of the compound with a few drops of conc. HNO₃ and conc. H₂SO₄ and then igniting the residue in an electric Bunsen at 500 °C. MoO₃ obtained was dissolved in 6*N* NaOH and then Mo was estimated as bis(8-hydroxyquinolino)dioxomolybdenum(VI). The studies on spectral (IR, reflectance, ¹H NMR and ESR) and magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by the methods reported earlier¹⁹. The mass spectrum of **1** was recorded on Waters Micromass Q-ToF Micro-mass Spectrometer.

Synthesis of 1 :

Acetoacetanilide (1.77 g, 10 mmol) and *o*-hydroxybenzylamine (1.23 g, 10 mmol) were refluxed in EtOH (50 mL) on a water bath for 1 h. The excess of solvent was evaporated and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature. The yellow compound separated out was suction filtered, washed with and recrystallized from EtOH and then dried over silica gel *in vacuo*. Yield 70%, m.p. 118 °C; anal. [C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₂; found (calcd)% C = 72.48(72.34), H = 6.23(6.38), N = 9.83(9.93); IR bands (cm⁻¹) : 3561 ν(OH)(intramolecular H-bond), 3066 ν(N—H)(intramolecular H-bond), 1628 ν(C=N)(azomethine), 1514 ν(C—O)Φ and 1200 ν(C—O)(enolic).

Syntheses of 2-6 :

1 (2.82 g, 10 mmol) was suspended in 25 mL of 0.8N NaOH solution and was stirred gently. The yellow coloured solution obtained was added slowly, while stirring to an aqueous solution of respective metal acetate or to a MeOH solution of bis(acetylacetonato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) (5 mmol). The pH of the solution was adjusted between 3–4 by adding acetic acid. The solution was then refluxed on a water bath for 5–7 h. The excess of solvent was evaporated and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature. The solid compound separated out was suction filtered, washed with and recrystallized from distilled water followed by solvent ether and then dried as mentioned above. Yield 35–50%.

Syntheses of 7-11 :

A MeOH solution (30 mL) of 1 (10 mmol) was added to a MeOH solution (50 mL) of the given metal acetate/bis(acetylacetonato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) (10 mmol). The solution was refluxed on a water bath for 2 h. A MeOH solution (20 mL) of MeONa (20 mmol) was then added to the above solution, while in hot. The solid compound separated out was suction filtered, washed with MeOH several times, followed by solvent ether and then dried as mentioned above. Yield 65–82%.

Conclusion :

On the basis of analytical data (Table 1), valence requirements, spectral and magnetic susceptibility measurements, it is proposed that 1 behaves as a monobasic bidentate ON donor ligand in 2-6 coordinating through its phenolic O and azomethine N atoms, while as a dibasic tridentate ONO donor ligand in 7-11 coordinating through its phenolic O, azomethine N and enolic O atoms. The data suggest a square-planar structure to 2, 7; a tetrahedral structure to 3, 8 and an octahedral structure to 4-6 and 9-11.

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